

PEDAGOGY

THE USE OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FUNCTIONAL LITERACY THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING

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Abstract

Today the teaching of foreign language, including English, is of particular importance. However, in order for language learning to be sufficiently effective and «authentic», conservative methods are not enough. Times change, society has new needs and demands, which means that the methods of quality English language teaching are changing. One of such methods is the method of using digital media in a foreign language lesson with the aim of developing critical thinking of schoolchildren. Currently, it is important to raise an active and developed in all directions personality. The ability to analyze, make important decisions, come to certain conclusions is the main component of critical thinking.

Topicality of this work is determined by the need of search and methodologically reasonable choice of the most effective ways of the usage digital media tools to develop learners' critical thinking.

The object of the research work is the process of teaching critical thinking in information educational environment.

The subject of the research work is various digital media tools used to develop critical thinking among learners (Internet resources, graphic organizers, software, etc.)

The aim of the research work is to explore the features of using digital media in foreign language lessons, to identify the significance and relevance of their implementation for developing critical thinking.

The objectives:

- to consider the existing approaches of methodologists and research scientists to the problem of developing critical thinking among learners;
- to identify and describe some techniques for developing critical thinking;
- to survey the specificity of digital media and their ability to develop learners' critical thinking;
- to implement methods of developing critical thinking through digital media in foreign language lessons;
- to analyze the techniques of developing critical thinking by means of digital media in foreign language lessons.

Research methods:

- analysis and synthesis of pedagogical and methodical literature on research issues;
- descriptive method;
- comparative method.

Keywords: modern educational technologies, schoolchildren, critical thinking, English as a foreign language, digital media.

The modern world has become difficult because of the acceleration of new technologies and the sophistication of global relations. This super-fast movement requires everyone to face many challenges, the consequences of which are ethical, social and environmental issues. The totality of these events claims realizing these problems, to understand them, to make a judgment quickly efficiently and responsibly. The future generation of Kazakhstan citizens is no exception. Acceleration of the methods used in the professions, the introduction of digital technologies in vocational edu-

cation, the opening of borders in practice and professional training teach young people to quickly cope with all these changes.

Therefore, education should provide children with all the means and conditions so that this adaptation to the world can be implemented and continue throughout their lives. Using critical thinking and learning it seems to be one of these necessary tools. From some thinkers and educators' point of view developing critical thinking will allow children to become enlightened citizens, able to ensure the development and sustainability of democracy. Therefore, interest in developing critical thinking among future specialists is increasing every

year. Supporters of critical thinking consider it important to develop critical thinking, and to teach children how to reason properly, not cram material.

Thinking is the highest form of brain activity that reflects the world, the most complex cognitive mental process inherent in human. Thinking is defined as «a state of indecision, hesitation, doubt» [1, 401]. As Leontyev stated, thinking is always an active process, it begins with a «presentation», that is, an object is presented to the consciousness; thinking takes place at the level of conscious [2, 7]. So, thinking begins with a problem situation, it is an analytical-synthetic activity.

It can be concluded that critical thinking is not associated with the ability to criticize, object and find flaws [3, 284]. It is important to help students see the diversity of the surrounding problems; only by fighting a particular problem, finding a way out of the current situation, does the student really think. It is important to teach children to think about the subtext, to set themselves problems and questions, as well as to create new ideas [4, 104].

Experimental work is a type of development associated with the experimental verification of scientific research results.

We consider the research conducted by us to be experimental work, because we set the task of identifying the skills of critical thinking in working on the foreign language text using a special set of exercises.

According to our assumption that the formation of critical thinking skills in the work on the foreign language text will be effective in the application of exercises and assignments based on digital tools, the essence of experimental work is to test our lesson plans aimed at developing critical thinking through digital media.

The experimental study aimed to verify the validity that the process of developing critical thinking skills will be more effective with the specially designed exercises and tasks through digital media in the work on the foreign language text.

In accordance with the goal we have identified the following objectives of the study:

1. To determine the level of critical thinking skills' formation in the work on the foreign language text.
2. To develop and test a set of exercises for developing critical thinking skills using digital media.
3. To analyze and summarize the results of experimental work, to formulate conclusion.

In the organization of practical work, we were guided by the following provisions:

1. Experimental work was carried out in natural conditions in accordance with the approved program of learning English.
2. The study involved deliberate changes in the educational process in accordance with the purpose of the work.

3. Experimental work assumed the study of the effectiveness and developed set of tasks through digital media aimed at developing critical thinking skills in the work on the foreign language text.

4. The experiment was conducted on students the same age.

The experiment was conducted during pedagogical practice. The study was attended by students of 8 classes (24 students). Our experimental work consisted of three stages:

1. Ascertaining
2. Formative
3. Controlling

Control and experimental groups were determined for checking. The choice was based on the analysis of students' progress in the 2022 academic year in English.

Quantitative analysis of the results of student performance indicates the homogeneity of these groups in the first group «5»- 4, «4»-8, «3»-0, «2»-0, and the second «5» - 3, «4»- 7, «3» - 2, «2» -0. Students in the two groups have approximately the same level of knowledge. The average score in the groups is 4.19.

Based on the quantitative analysis, we see that the gap between the groups is small. Based on this, we consider the first subgroup as experimental, and the second subgroup as control.

At the ascertaining stage, students of the first (EG) and second (KG) groups were offered a text for the initial verification of critical thinking skills' formation. At this stage we didn't use digital media tools.

In the first exercise, students were asked to answer questions that check their knowledge of history.

The questions seemed difficult for students. Students found it complicated to answer questions related to people who changed the world.

In the process of working on the text, exercises were proposed that test the understanding of the text as a whole, as well as the ability to find the main idea of the text and the location of the text in three logical parts. That directly indicates the level of critical thinking [5, 21].

We concluded that students' critical thinking skills in working on the foreign language text are formed at low and medium levels [6, 12].

The evaluation criteria were:

High level is a grade «5», if the student scored more than 15 points (1 task-1 point);

Middle level is a grade «4», if the student scored from 10 to 15 points;

Low level is a grade «3», if the student scored less than 10 points.

Diagram №1 Comparative analysis (before the experiment)

Comparing the data on the two groups, we can conclude that the difference between the average scores and the level of formation of critical thinking skills in working on the foreign language text is small. Basically, students have an average level of critical thinking skills' formation.

The next task of the initial ascertaining stage of experimental work is to determine the conditions.

As a variable condition of experimental training is the fact that the KG (12 students) classes were conducted according to the traditional method in English lessons, and in EG (12 students) we implemented drafted lesson plans using digital media.

Permanent conditions include:

- The study of the same amount of training material for EG and KG;
- Establishment of common didactic problems;
- The same final control tasks for two groups to determine the level of developing critical thinking [7, 15].

Summing up the first stage of experimental work, we reached the conclusion, that the difference between the average scores and the level of formation of critical thinking skills in working on the foreign language text is small. Basically, students have an average level that responds the requirements of education.

The basis for demonstrating the types of exercises used in multimedia programs was the program «English: The Way to Perfection: Intermediate», which consists of two CD-ROM and 6 chapters (units). Each Chapter comprises 5 lessons devoted to one of the speech activity's types (Speaking, Reading, Listening and Writing), with the focus on the development of students' communication skills. In each chapter 2 lessons of 5 are devoted to developing students' speech skills.

Each lesson is made up of 6-7 parts:

- Presentation;
- Activities;
- Vocabulary Practice;
- Grammar;
- Grammar Practice - in lessons for developing listening skills;
- Role Practice - in lessons for developing speech skills;
- Role Play - in lessons for developing speech skills;

- Dialog Builder - in lessons for developing speech skills;
- Construction Kit - the lessons for developing writing skills;
- Multiple Choices - in lessons for developing reading skills;
- Fill In - in lessons for developing reading skills.

Each part performs its functions. All exercises are implemented on the computer.

In these lessons students will find many samples of useful written documents.

They will serve as an example for self-writing such texts. During the lessons students:

- develop the skills necessary for competent writing in English;
- learn how to write different types of documents, letters, complaints, etc [8, 35].

As we said earlier, multimedia programs implement modern approaches to teaching English as a cognitive-communicative, personality-centered, linguocultural.

The most productive multimedia presentations have established themselves, in which after explaining or presenting the material, exercises for fixing or control are inserted. These exercises, students are doing directly from the screen individually or in the front. The ability to show the correct answer allows you to organize an inter-or self-test quickly and efficiently.

Also, in our lessons we made efforts to encourage students to get involved in a creative approach to learning. At the end of the work on a certain topic, we asked students to prepare creative work using web-sites such as «Google presentations», «Slide dog», «Rowshorts» and etc., and the program «Power Point», «Excel» or simply «Word». We offered students different topics for projects, but we proceed from the practical importance of this topic for the students themselves. There are just some of the topics: «The city of military glory», «How to make your city attractive for tourists» etc. So, students provide their brochures, booklets, presentations or simply abstracts and projects that are presented in the classroom. The school has an interactive Board «Promethean» installed in the classroom. Using special markers on the screen, you can display any information,

highlight important other color, work with any computer programs. In addition, it has the function of a conventional Board, where the «chalk» becomes a marker. They can write and erase the writing with an eraser.

In our opinion, the success of developing critical thinking through digital media depends on compliance with a number of conditions, such as:

- using of strategies for developing critical thinking;
- using of a set of exercises for developing critical thinking;
- systematic work on developing of critical thinking [9, 11];

We believe that the developed exercises motivate students to improve critical thinking, their horizons and provide interest in working on the foreign language text.

Summing up this work, it will be recalled that the aim of the research work is to explore the features of using digital media in foreign language lessons for developing critical thinking.

The use of digital media's tools expands the educational process, enhances its practical orientation, contributes to increasing student motivation and developing the student's intellectual and creative abilities and creates conditions for their successful self-realization in the future. Therefore, analysis of existing techniques was carried out, additional techniques on digital codes and multimedia program «English: the way to Perfection» were applied. All these methods were aimed at developing the critical thinking of ninth-graders in English classes. As a result, we managed to increase the level of critical thinking of ninth grade students by 60 percent.

We hope that the material of this study presented in a generalized and systematic form can help the teacher of foreign languages (not only English) in their professional activities of teaching foreign languages in

different types of educational institutions for developing critical thinking through digital media.

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